

EFFECTIVENESS OF AUDIO-LINGUAL METHODS AT SECONDARY EDUCATION IN BANGLADESH

Md. Harun Rashid^{1*} and Md. Jahirul Islam²

^{1*}(Faculty of Modern language and communication, Universiti Putra Malaysia, Malaysia.)

²(Faculty of Modern language and communication, Universiti Putra Malaysia, Malaysia.)

DOI: [10.333329/joell.7.1.36](https://doi.org/10.333329/joell.7.1.36)

ABSTRACT

In this research, I limit the discussion by stating the following question. How does the Audio-lingual Method effective in Bangladesh? The objective of this study is to explain the effectiveness of the Audio-lingual method in Bangladesh. It is expected that the result will provide a deeper understanding of the uses of the Audio-lingual Method and can be used as a teaching method for English language teachers and students. The study implemented an experiment test to accomplish the objectives. The participants of this study were the student of class 8 to 10. The academies of this study were from various secondary level Schools at Tongi in Bangladesh. The number of the School was five and our main purpose was to find out the problems of the audio-lingual method in the field of secondary education. As most of the teachers and students do not know about the method thus the research was fully unable to explore the problems of the audio-lingual method in terms of Bangladesh.

keywords: *Audio-lingual method, Secondary education in Bangladesh, English teaching method.*

INTRODUCTION

The Audio-lingual method was used at the Second World War to teach soldiers sufficient fluency to infiltrate enemy territory, it became as the 'army method' (Sharpe, 2018) It has militaristic features in which reside both its strongest and its weakest elements. Since the 1940s, the definitive solution to successful ESL instruction has been discovering many times. Like bestsellers, pop stars, and ice-cream flavors, second-Language theories and methodologies enjoy a few afternoons or years in the spotlight and then stumble into the dusk of old age. There is always another tried-and-true methodology from yet another expert theorist who may or may not has had first-hand experience learning a second language. Before the late nineteenth century, second-language instruction mirrored the so-called Classical Method of teaching Latin and Greek; lessons were based on mental-aerobics exercises repetition drills and out-of-context vocabulary drills as well as lots of reading and translations of ancient texts. Brown notes that languages were "not being taught primarily to learn oral/aural communication, but to learn for the sake of being 'scholarly' or for reading proficiency". Theories of second-language acquisition did not start to pop up until the instructional objective became oral competence. This study aims to find out the effectiveness of the audio-lingual method in Bangladeshi perspective.

Britto (2017) stated that the audio-lingual method which provided a powerful framework that not only yielded a set of principles with the guide of generations educators. The study is to discover the technique to implement the audio-lingual method and its problem in the classroom. The study also observes the present situation of the audio-lingual method at secondary level educations in Bangladesh.

The study is to explain the usefulness of the Audio-lingual method in Bangladesh's perspective and the result of this study will provide a more profound understanding as well as the effectiveness of the Audio-lingual Method for English language teachers and students. Till now in Bangladesh, most of the teachers and students are not well known about the method. Therefore, this article discovered the

technique of audio-lingual methods and their problems in Bangladesh. The aim of this research is the implementation of the audio-lingual method on English teachers and students of Bangladesh. In this article, we found that the audio-lingual method is the mode of language instruction based on the behaviorist approach and the method is to create communicative competence by giving wide-ranging repetition and drilling to the student in the secondary level schools.

HYPOTHESIS

This research is a designee on the audio-lingual method. According to our experience, we anticipate that the method could be a very new thing for the teachers and students. Our Government already introduced the new curriculum. However, the question, is it reached all around Bangladesh?

LITERATURE REVIEW

The Audio-Lingual Method puts more emphasis on mechanical repetition, the use of tape records, film strips, etc. Next, the principles of The Audio-Lingual Method, as written by Larsen-Freeman (1986: 43-45), namely (1) the goal of teaching is to use language communicatively; (2) the teacher is to lead, control and direct the students' behaviour and the students should follow the directions and respond as accurately, as rapidly as possible; (3) new vocabularies and structures are presented through dialogue (imitation, repetition, drill); (4) explicit grammar rules are not provided and culture information is contextualized in the dialogue; (5) most interaction is between teacher and students initiated by teacher; interaction between students is directed by the teacher; (6) the level of complexity of the speech is graded; selected from simple to more complicated and then put into habit-forming; (7) pronunciation is taught from the beginning; (8) target language is used in the classroom; and (9) students' errors are to be avoided (Anabokay, 2019).

Simultaneously, developing oral skills utilizing controlled practice and repetitive drills (ALM) for teaching discrete skills could help the learners to enhance their communicative competence at a later stage. After all, linguistic competence is a concomitant of communicative competence. Even

the preservice programs do contribute as the building blocks of the teaching process for communicative purposes (Khan et al., 2019). The Audiolingual method of teaching and the Vaughan method share similar objectives. For instance, both the Vaughan and Audiolingual methods share the core objective of enabling learners to use correct grammar and pronunciation. Also, the Audiolingual method assists learners to respond accurately and quickly while engaging in conversations both in and out of the classroom setting. Teachers, who use the Audiolingual method, intended to provide learners with sufficient knowledge of vocabulary to use incorrect grammar patterns (Bagheri, 2019).

The instructor explains how to pronounce and practice grammatical formulas orally while correcting any mistakes made. The teacher gives the class positive energy and boosts participation in the class. Classes that use the Vaughan method of teaching are more active and full of energy and students barely get bored or switch off in such classes. They tend to be very attentive, due to the drills which may be prompted by the teacher at any moment. The instructor, therefore, makes the students keen on what is being taught. Consequently, a student's progress in an EFL program is enhanced significantly. A teacher is, therefore, the motor that keeps the Vaughan method of teaching up and running (Pedraza, 2016). The audio-lingual method (ALM) was developed in 1940 in the US, paralleling the British "structural-situational method" (Rilling, 2018) ALM continued as a packaged methodology through the 1970s with some techniques still being used in English Second Language. Sharpe, A.E 2018 The audio-lingual method, based on Skinner's stimulus-response psychology was adopted, It was implemented in slightly different ways by the four departments of education responsible for white education in the four provinces. In the second education, students have to learn four major skills, i.e. listening, speaking, reading and writing (Ekawati, 2017). As this method was used during the Second World War to teach soldiers, sufficient fluency to infiltrate enemy territory, it became known as an 'army method'. It has militaristic features in which reside both its strongest and its weakest elements.

Abu-Melhem (2009) pointed out that the ALM approach results in a lack of student motivation.

A glance through the past century of language, teaching gives an interesting picture of various methodologies in the field of foreign language teaching. The sudden breakout of World War II heightened the need for proficient language speakers. The US Army provided a fund for specific language courses that focused on aural-oral skills under the program called the Army Specialized Training Program (ASTP). Many American universities contributed to this program. Financial support for language research and development resulted from the National Defense Education Act (NDEA 1957) contributed to the development of audio-bilingualism. The Audio-lingual method is a method of foreign language teaching which emphasizes the teaching of listening and speaking before reading and writing. It uses dialogues as the main form of language presentation and drills as the main training techniques. The mother's tongue is discouraged in the classroom.

Charles C. Fries, director of the University of Michigan's English Language Institute, the first of its kind in the US, found that the learning structure or grammar was the starting point for the student. In other words, it was up to the students to recite sentence patterns and basic grammatical structures. The student was only given "enough vocabulary to do such exercises". Richards, J.C. et al., Fries, then incorporated the principles of behavioral psychology developed by B.F. Skinner into this method.

TECHNIQUES OF THE AUDIO-LINGUAL METHOD

Larsen-Freeman provides expanded descriptions of some common or typical techniques closely associated with the Audio-lingual Method. The listing here is as follows:

1. Dialogue memorization Students memorize and open dialogue using mimicry and applied to role-play.
2. Backward Build-up Expansion Drill Teacher breaks a line into several parts; students repeat each part starting at the end of the sentence and "expanding" backward

through the sentence, adding each part in sequence.

3. Repetition drill Students repeat teacher is model as quickly and accurately as possible.
4. Chain drill Students ask and answer each other one by one in a circular chain around the classroom.
5. Single-slot Substitution drill Teacher states a line from the dialogue and then uses a word or phrase as a "cue" that students when repeating the line, must substitute into the sentence in the correct place.
6. Multiple-slot Substitution drills the same as the single slot drill, except that there are multiple cues to substitute into the line.
7. Transformation drill Teacher provides a sentence that must turn into something else, for example, a question to turn into a statement, an active sentence to turn into a negative statement, etc.
8. Question and Answer drill Students should answer or ask questions very quickly.
9. Use Minimal Pairs Analysis, the teacher selects a pair of words that sound identical except for a single sound that typically poses a difficulty for the learners-students are to pronounce and differentiate the two words.
10. Complete the dialogue Selected words are erased from a line in the dialogue-students must find and insert.
11. Grammar games various games designed to practice a grammar point in context, using lots of repetition.

RESEARCH METHODOLOGY

We used collaborative materials related to the audio-lingual method sample. We collected the data from Bangladeshi secondary level schools in Tongi areas. We have conducted this research in two phases. First, we have conducted primary research without saying them anything about the topic then we took another exam on the same question after giving them all the information on the method, which was to answer the research questions and rectify the hypothesis. The primary research has been conducting with the two-questionnaire survey. Five research questions we prepared for the students, and

five questions prepared for the teachers, included with agree, disagree and strongly agreed on the questionnaire. We tested Listening skills, speaking skills, classroom observations, and face-to-face student and teacher interviews. Seventy students in each class and four teachers in each institution were surveys. The data was analyzed qualitative research and the inherent patterns in the data interpreted through an appropriate explanation following the questions. We have been observing every question. To find materials on the web we have used search engines like Google or Yahoo, reference sites, and news sites. This literature review has contributed to our primary research extensively.

DATA ANALYSIS

Questionnaire and interviews for student

No	Question	Agreed	Disagreed	Average
01	Did your teacher give you an idea about the audio-lingual method?	3%	88%	9%
02	Did you find the method suitable for you?	76%	12%	12%
03	Did your teacher give homework while interpreting it?	9%	86%	5%
04	Are you feeling bored with the repetition drill?	58%	18%	22%
05	Did you learn anything creative from this method?	52%	19%	29%

1. Did your teacher give you an idea about the audio-lingual method?

The data is saying that 88% of the students disagreed with the question and 3% said they knew it. 9% of students said as average. They said they only heard of the name, According to the teachers voting, we find out most of the teachers do not know the (ALM) method. However, we saw the eagerness of knowing and learning more in teacher and student. Their answer was not the same after the second test. They said they did not have an idea of this method or did not know this kind of learning process has a name but they said some of their teachers use this method at times.

2. Did you find the method suitable for you?

This is a thoughtful question for the students based on the previous graph. We shared the audio-lingual method to the student and the student understands that this method is suitable for them to learn the language. In this, graph 76% of students agreed to the question, 12 % thought it would work for them. In addition, 12% thought this could not do any better.

3. Did your teacher give homework while interpreting it?

According to data in this graph, 86% of students did not get any homework while interpreting the method in the classroom. 5% of students said they didn't understand our question (they entered the class almost half an hour later we started our survey). In addition, 9% of students agreed. They said through their teacher does not know about the method but his teaching technique matches the method.

4. Are you feeling bored with the repetition drill?

We found, from the thoughtful answer, 58% of students assume that the repetition is going to be boring. Most of them said nobody loves repetition at the same thing for longer hours. Where 22% of them said that this is confusing, as they did not get to work on it and 18% of students directly disagreed with the question but all are memorize with repetition. Both of the time test student's answers like the same way. At first, they did not know about the method but they answered based on the word "boring". It

somewhat also stands for students of our country, the education system boring.

5. Did you learn anything creative from this method?

According to the survey, 52% of students agreed that the method would be creative though they did not know of it. They thought that the method would take them one step closer to become a good teacher. However, 29% of students said there has an average possibility of getting anything creative from the method. The other 19% of students disagreed with the question. They also said anything new for leaning gives a new experience, increases learnability and gives an idea about creative things.

QUESTIONNAIRES FOR TEACHERS AND SHORT INTERVIEW:

1.What is your idea about the audio-lingual method?

According to the teacher, only 18% of teachers have a primary idea about (ALM). On the other hand, 29% of teachers said they know half about it on average. However, 53% of teachers do not know about the (ALM) method. It is clear that a large number of teachers from the secondary level in Bangladesh have no idea about the Audio-lingual method. Where some of them have little idea about the (ALM) method but this is sad because only 24% of teachers know about the method though it is almost extinct.

2. Do you think it is a better way for language learning?

In this response, 56% of teachers agreed with positive and 33% of them said it is an average method whereas only a few 11% of teachers think that this method can do any better. After knowing about the method, we saw a completely different result in the graph. Comparing the first graph, most of the teachers agreed that this method could be better. Where in the first graph was seen that most of them have no idea about this method? From this difference, we understand one thing that we need to change something in our text.

3. Do you practice dialogue with students or chain drills in the classroom?

According to data, just 7% of the teachers agreed to the question that they use dialogue/chain drills in the classroom. There 17% of them gave their opinion on average but a large number of teachers did practice in the classroom works based on the Audio-lingual method. It seems like the graph has disappointed us again. The data is saying that 76% of teachers said directly "no" practice in the classroom. The thing is most of the teachers are not familiar with this method.

4. Did you get an invitation to attending a seminar on the audio-lingual method?

In this reply, 89% of teachers said they don't get any invitation on (ALM) seminar, Only 5% of teachers said "yes" to the question. On the other hand, 6% of teachers said they got an invitation in the past but did not felt interested in attending one. After knowing about the method they felt interested to attend the seminars base on the method. In the second observation, they answered was completely diverse and seem interested.

5. Do you have any recommendations on the (ALM) method?

In this response, 91% of the teachers have a recommended for use in classroom compulsory. 6% seen to remain silent and others only 3% said no. This change has simply amazed us. The teachers seem very much interested in adopting the method in their classroom. They think the audio-lingual method will help learner's to learn the language with co-operation and spontaneously. They found it very much effective, but in the first exam, they did not understand our question and unable to place the answer. As my observation, we understand one thing that they have a hunger for learning language following by (ALM).

No	Question	Positive	Negative	Average
01	What is your idea about the audio-lingual method?	18%	53%	29%
02	Do you think it is a better way for language learning?	56%	11%	33%
03	Do you practice dialogue with students or chain drills in the classroom?	7%	76%	17%
04	Did you get an invitation to attending a seminar on the audio-lingual method?	5%	89%	6%
05	Do you have any recommendations on the (ALM) method?	91%	3%	6%

FINDINGS

The main point of this research results in the implementation of the audio-lingual method in English teachers and students of Bangladesh. In this article, we got that the audio-lingual method (ALM) is the mode of language instruction based on the behaviorist approach. Brown (1994) argued on the audio-lingual method because of some key features, new material is present in dialog form, repetitive drills, memorization of a set of phrases, etc. The aim of this method is to create communicative competence by giving wide-ranging repetition and drilling to the student in the secondary levels schools.

As we realized in this article they have lots of roles for a teacher on the audio-lingual method. The teacher had to take the main pressure as if he constantly repeats this thing. They want to teach but it does not matter how much time it takes.

RECOMMENDATION AND CONCLUSION

According to our observation, the result of the audio-lingual method is different in our country. Because very few know about the audio-lingual method when they said taught about it. They gave their judgment without interpreting this method and the field. However, they consider the method enthusiastic and spontaneous in the research. Teachers felt that their part will be huge but they would love to take it. This method helps to teach in the classroom, as a result, students feel it easy and fun. They might learn anything that is not easy to catch without pressuring the brain. They were happy because no will homework in this method but they are learning in the classroom. The overall survey shows that in a Bangladeshi perspective, it should adopt. In some of the fields, this method seen adopted like the English coaching center or Language learning center in Bangladesh. It also turned out to be useful. Overall, we can say that the audio-lingual method is an innovative method for teaching in academies and it should be an excellent medium for language learning in the secondary classroom. They have lots of think related to the audio-lingual method but we work and highlight the recent situation of the audio-lingual method in the classroom. Most of the teachers do not have any idea about the audio-lingual method. We also focused on secondary levels schoolteachers and students, as they were from Bangla medium schools. They seemed nervous while we used them in an English questionnaire. This area is not enough to find out the real problem so if the next researcher could be found deeply about the (ALM).

The audio-lingual method definitely has pros and cons in a secondary level classroom for language learning. The disadvantages and negative implications can overcome the audio-lingual method. If a slightly and more eclectic approach to second language teaching and learning in the classroom. Some teachers may stubbornly hold fast to the rules of the (ALM) and refuse to stray from it. The

objective of second languages, teaching should be questionable according to the recent classroom situation. The goal of aiding learners in achieving communicative competence with the audio-lingual method. It does not matter what method is used in the classroom, as long as learners gain valuable communicative skills. It is the teacher's responsibility to determine here teaching goals and appropriate methods to use where an eclectic one might better achieve those goals. Therefore, the teacher of a second language must be prepared to modify and adjust their methods and realize which method is sweet able and flexible in the classroom to teach the language.

REFERENCES

- Abu-Melhim, A. 2009. Re-evaluating the effectiveness of the audio-lingual method in teaching English to speakers of other languages. In *the International Forum of Teaching and Studies*, 5(2): 39-45. American Scholars Press, Inc.
- Anabokay, Y. M. 2019. TEF Method in Indonesia. *International Journal of Linguistics, Literature, and Culture*, 5(2): 13-24. <https://sloap.org/journals/index.php/ijllc/>.
- Bagheri, M. 2019. Effects of the Vaughan Method in Comparison with the Audiolingual Method and the Communicative Language Teaching on Iranian Advanced EFL Learners' Speaking Skill. *International Journal of Instruction*, 12(2): 81-98.
- Britto, R. 2008. The dissipation of methods in ESL: Expanding to fill the void. *Journal of education*, 188(3): 75-84.
- Ekawati, A. D. 2017. The Effect of TPR and Audio-Lingual Method in Teaching Vocabulary Viewed from Students' IQ. *Journal of ELT Research*, 2(2): 55-65.
- Khan, R. M. I., Radzuan, N. R. M., Shahbaz, M., & Ibrahim, A. H. 2019. Efficacy of methodological practices undertaken by Saudi English teachers in public schools during their formative phase. *English Review: Journal of English Education*, 7(2): 47-54.
- Pedraza M. M. (2016). Different approaches to teaching English as a second language. MA Thesis. Retrieved from <http://uvadoc.uva.es/handle/10324/19234>.
- Rilling, S. 2018. The audio-lingual method, *The TESOL Encyclopedia of English language teaching*. Wily Blackwell.
- Savignon, S. J. 1991. Communicative Language Teaching: State of the Art. *TESOL Quarterly*, 25(2): 261-277.
- Schneider man, N., McIntosh, R. C., & Antoni, M. H. 2019. Psychosocial risk and management of physical diseases. *Journal of behavioral medicine*, 42(1): 16-33.
- Sharpe, A. E. 2018. An evaluation of the audio-lingual method. *International forum of teaching and studies journal*, 5(2): 1-12.